

Gravimetric, Magnetic and Diffuse Reflectance Spectroscopic Studies of fully hydrated Nickel exchanged A-Zeolites

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Five samples of Ni A-zeolites (16.6–76.6% exchanged) were prepared and investigated. Gravimetric, magnetic and diffuse reflectance spectroscopic studies showed that the Ni^{II} ions are octahedrally coordinated in fully hydrated type A-zeolite. Magnetic results indicated that the reciprocal of molar susceptibility decreases with increasing Ni^{II} content in the zeolitic framework. The replacement of Na^I by Ni^{II} increases the zeolitic water. In general, the hypsochromic shift of the band maxima of the fully hydrated Ni A-zeolites was recorded.

THE catalytic properties of incorporated cations in zeolite matrices are strongly dependent on the nature and distribution of the cations within the framework¹. Recently transition metal exchanged zeolites attracted much attention and have been researched extensively using different techniques. The prominent feature of zeolites is that they form within their aluminosilicate framework a variety of complexes upon interaction of transition metal zeolites with various organic or inorganic substances. By using myriad of techniques²⁻⁶ the framework structure of the synthetic type A-zeolite has been established, and information obtained on the coordination and location of transition metal ions to preserve electroneutrality of the framework. The availability of synthetic single crystals of zeolite-A, enabled Seff² to locate the position of several cations, both in hydrated and dehydrated samples.

Since the pioneering work of Klier⁴ and Klier and Ralek⁵ on hydrated Ni A-zeolites using reflectance spectroscopic techniques, several authors reported⁷⁻¹¹ work dealing with the physical characteristics and spectroscopic properties of hydrated Ni A-zeolites, but the information is scanty. This paper describes the systematic study of the lattice structures and formation of Ni^{II} complexes with H₂O molecules in the zeolitic cavities of five fully hydrated samples of zeolite type A, using three different techniques, viz. thermogravimetry, reflectance spectroscopy and magnetic susceptibility. Reflectance spectroscopy is potentially one of the most powerful experimental techniques to gain information on the electronic structure of the components of heterogeneous dispersed systems and their external as well as internal surfaces. Here the combined results of gravimetric and spectroscopic measurements are used for assigning the structure of nickel in zeolitic structure. The magnetic properties of Ni^{II} ions are also sensitive to environment,

so bulk susceptibility measurements are also applied to find the structure of Ni^{II} in the zeolites.

Experimental

The synthetic Na A-zeolite (lot no. 4941040757) used for cation exchange with Ni^{II} was supplied by Union Carbide, U.S.A. The synthetic Na A was in the form of the powder without binder with unit cell composition, Na₁₂ [(AlO₂)₁₂ (SiO₂)₁₂].nH₂O¹². Five zeolite samples having exchange levels of 1.0, 2.4, 3.15, 3.9 and 4.6 Ni^{II} ions per unit cell were prepared by ion-exchange from nickel(II) chloride solutions. The methods for the preparation and chemical analysis of Ni A-zeolites were the same as previously described¹². For each sample, hydrated Na A-zeolite (5 g) was slurried in deionised water (75 cm³) and pH was reduced from 11.2 to 7 by adding very slowly very dilute hydrochloric acid (0.01 mol dm⁻³) with constant stirring with a magnetic stirrer. For each sample, the temperature of cation-exchanging slurry was kept at 353 K. All the fully hydrated Ni A-zeolites were green in colour. The structural integrity was examined by X-ray diffraction and physical adsorption of krypton at 77 K, which indicated no loss of structure resulting from the exchange process. Volumetric analysis confirmed that each Ni^{II} ion replaced exactly two Na^I ions. The five samples of Ni Na A-zeolites prepared with the general unit cell formula,

where, $x=1.0, 2.4, 3.15, 3.9$ and 4.6 , and $30 < m < 48$. Water contents of the zeolites were obtained gravimetrically using a McBain spring (sensitivity 1 mm \approx 4.411 mg), with a liquid nitrogen cooled trap situated near to the balance, attached to a standard high vacuum systems of pyrex glass. The high vacuum system could be evacuated to 1×10^{-6} torr.

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TABLE 1—ANALYSIS AND PREPARATIVE CONDITIONS OF NICKEL(II) EXCHANGED A-ZEOLITES

Sample attempted to prepare	Molarity of original solution of NiCl ₂ × 10 ⁻³ mol dm ⁻³ *	Period for cation-exchanged h	pH of cation-exchanged sultry	% Exchang	Composition of cation-exchanged sample	Colour of the hydrated samples
Ni ₁ A	1.14	12	8.0	100	Ni ₁ A	Very light green
Ni _{2.4} A	2.85	36	6.5	97.8	Ni _{2.4} A	Light green
Ni _{3.15} A	3.55	50	6.4	98.6	Ni _{3.15} A	Green
Ni _{3.9} A	4.56	70	6.4	88.47	Ni _{3.9} A	Bright green
Ni _{4.6} A	5.71	50	6.0	91.84	Ni _{4.6} A	Bright green

* 200 cm³ of x M of NiCl₂ solution was used for each zeolite.

The quantity of the samples taken in the bucket of the spring were 150–300 mg of the fully hydrated weight. Each sample was outgassed at 620 K in vacuum for several hours until the sample became completely dehydrated.

Magnetic susceptibility measurements were made on only three fully hydrated samples, i.e. Ni_{1.0}A, Ni_{2.4}A and Ni_{4.6}A in the powder form using a specially constructed Pyrex flat-bottomed tube on a Gouy magnetic balance. The balance was calibrated by using CuSO₄·5H₂O powder. It was shown⁷ that Ni A-zeolite obeys the Curie–Weiss law with $\theta \approx 0$, so magnetic moments were calculated from measurements at 298 K.

The diffuse reflectance spectra recorded at 25° in the range 11 500–32 500 cm⁻¹ with a Pye Unicam SP 800 spectrophotometer using a SP 890 diffuse reflectance attachment. The reflectance spectra of the hydrated Ni A-zeolites in the powder form were recorded by using a recessed aluminium disc.

Results

Table 1 shows a summary of analysis and preparative condition of nickel(II) exchanged A-zeolites. The chemical composition and water contents of the zeolites are given in Table 2. It may be seen

TABLE 2—CHEMICAL COMPOSITION OF Ni A-ZEOLITES

Sample*	Cations and water molecules per unit cell		
	Na ^I	Na ^{II}	H ₂ O
NiA	12	—	29
Ni _{1.0} A	10	1.0	32
Ni _{2.4} A	7.2	2.4	34
Ni _{3.15} A	5.70	3.15	39.3
Ni _{3.9} A	4.2	3.9	45.3
Ni _{4.6} A	2.8	4.6	47.8

* Where 'A' is abbreviation for configuration, [(AlO₂)₁(SiO₂)₁₃]¹³⁻.

from Table 2 that the number of water molecules is related to the number of Ni^{II} ions present in the cell. The gravimetric results are expressed as the numbers of H₂O molecules per unit cell of the zeolite. A summary of the results of magnetic susceptibility measurements of hydrated Ni A-zeolites is given in Table 3. The measured susceptibilities were corrected for the effects of the small amount of ferromagnetic impurity (7) in zeolite A.

The result shows that the reciprocal of molar susceptibility (χ_M^{-1}) decreases with increasing Ni^{II} content of the zeolite. The values also indicate that magnetic moment (μ_{eff}) increases with increasing Ni^{II} ions concentration in the zeolite.

TABLE 3—MAGNETIC PROPERTIES OF FULLY HYDRATED NICKEL(II) EXCHANGED A-ZEOLITES

Zeolite	χ_M^{-1}	μ_{eff} B.M.
Ni ₁ A	208.3	3.43
Ni _{2.4} A	178.7	3.65
Ni _{4.6} A	146.0	4.00

The diffuse reflectance spectra of fully hydrated Ni₁A, Ni_{2.4}A, Ni_{3.15}A, Ni_{3.9}A and Ni_{4.6}A-zeolites are shown in Fig. 1, by curves 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5, respectively. Curve 6 is the transmittance spectrum of aqueous nickel(II) chloride. Curve 6 shows the bands at 13 350, 14 850 and 25 150 cm⁻¹. Fig. 1 shows that the band maxima of Ni₁A, Ni_{2.4}A, Ni_{3.15}A, Ni_{3.9}A and Ni_{4.6}A lie at 26 500, 26 100, 26 500, 26 600 and 26 250 cm⁻¹, respectively.

Fig 1. Comparison of diffuse reflectance spectra of hydrated Ni^{II} A-zeolites and transmittance spectrum of NiCl₂ solution ; (1) Ni₁A, (2) Ni_{2.4}A, (3) Ni_{3.15}A, (4) Ni_{3.9}A, (5) Ni_{4.6}A, and (6) aqueous NiCl₂.

Discussion

Table 2 shows that the number of water molecules per unit cell of hydrated Ni A-zeolites increases with increasing the number of Ni^{II} ions in the zeolite. Breck^{1,2} reported that the presence of different cations in the voids of zeolite type A affects the pore volume. A small divalent cation increases the

intrazeolitic volume by reducing the total number of cations and increasing the space unoccupied. According to valence rule, 2Na^+ ions were exchanged by 1Ni^{2+} ion, and that the ionic radii¹⁴ for Ni^{2+} and Na^+ ions are 0.69 and 0.95 Å, respectively; therefore, the space occupied in the cavities by water molecules increases by increasing the Ni^{2+} ions in the intrazeolitic structure. In addition, Ni^{2+} ions have the capability of forming strongly coordinated complexes with water molecules in which the latter are tightly packed, thus increasing the zeolitic water. The results of Table 2 also agree reasonable well with the literature values⁹⁻¹⁰. Dyer and Wilson⁹ and Coughlan *et al.*¹⁰ also reported the increase of water content per unit cell of a number of hydrated Ni A-zeolites with the increasing degrees of exchange.

It is well known¹⁵ that Ni^{2+} in aqueous NiCl_2 exists as hexaquo complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6]^{2+}$. Fig. 1 shows that the Ni^{2+} ions in fully hydrated Ni_1A , $\text{Ni}_{3.4}\text{A}$, $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$, $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ and $\text{Ni}_{4.6}\text{A}$, have electronic spectra which except for a hypsochromic shift of band maxima at *ca.* 1350, 950, 1350, 1450 and 1100 cm^{-1} , respectively, match the spectrum of the $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ complex, indicating that in hydrated Ni A-zeolites the Ni^{2+} ions are octahedrally coordinated by zeolitic water. Moreover, the following reasons also propose that Ni^{2+} ions in hydrated type A-zeolite exist as hexaquo-forming octahedral complexes. (i) Table 2 indicates that in hydrated Ni A-zeolites the $\text{H}_2\text{O}-\text{Ni}^{2+}$ ratio (as an average) is greater than 6, therefore, Ni^{2+} ions are assumed to be fully aquated with octahedrally coordinated water molecules. (ii) Table 3 shows that the magnetic moments of hydrated Ni A-zeolites are in range of 3.8 ± 0.2 B.M. which is close to the value expected for octahedral nickel complex^{7,15,16}, $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$. (iii) Both the hydrated samples of Ni A-zeolites and solution of NiCl_2 were green (similar spectra). In addition, there is general agreement^{9,10,14,17,18} that in the green complex the nickel ion is octahedrally coordinated to six water molecules.

It has been reported by Firor and Seff¹¹ by using X-ray diffraction technique that all the Ni^{2+} ions of fully hydrated Ni_3A -zeolite lie in the large cavity (α -cage), each Ni^{2+} ion being six-coordinated by three water molecules and three oxide ions in the framework. On the other hand, according to Coughlan *et al.*¹⁰, when more than 9Na^+ ions are exchanged by Ni^{2+} ions in type A-zeolite, then Ni ions replace Na ions at the 8-oxygen rings (site II), causing structural instability. But our results do not agree with the latter view on the following counts. (i) The monolayer equivalent areas measured¹³ by the adsorption of krypton at 77 K of NaA and Ni_1A were very low as compared to other samples and about the same, *i.e.* 27 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$. This indicates that 2Na^+ ions have been replaced by 1Ni^{2+} ion from 6-rings (site I) of β -cavity (sodalite unit) and 8-rings (site II) are partially blocked by Na^+ ions. Thus first Ni^{2+} ion enters the β -cavity of the zeolite forming the hexaquo

complex, $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$. As compared to Ni_1A , the high surface areas of $\text{Ni}_{3.4}\text{A}$ (338 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$), $\text{Ni}_{3.15}\text{A}$ (306 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$) and $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ (278 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$) showed the displacement of Na^+ ions from the 8-rings (windows of the large cavities). (ii) The identical electronic spectra (Fig. 1) of Ni_1A and aqueous NiCl_2 (both samples of green colour) confirm the existence of one Ni^{2+} ion as hexaquo complex within the sodalite cavities of all the five samples studied. (iii) The χ_M^{-1} and μ_{eff} values (Table 3) of fully hydrated Ni_1A are 203 and 3.43 B.M., respectively, suggesting the hexaquo octahedral structure of nickel⁷. (iv) Dyer and Wilson⁹ reported the existence of one Ni^{2+} ion in the β -cavity of hydrated zeolite type A, where it is fully hydrated and form $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ complex.

The values of reciprocal molar susceptibility measured as a function of Ni^{2+} ions content of fully hydrated samples (Table 3) agree, within experimental error, with the values reported by Egerton and Vickerman⁷. They assumed that these values indicate the octahedral coordination of Ni^{2+} ions. But here the decrease in reciprocal of molar susceptibility with increase in Ni^{2+} ions content of the samples has not been understood.

Fig. 1 shows an increase in absorbance and band shifts to higher energy of fully hydrated NiA-zeolites, but this behaviour is not systematic as was observed in fully hydrated CoA-zeolites towards low frequency¹⁹. Similar hypsochromic shifts of band maxima of hydrated NiA-zeolites have been reported by Klier²⁰, Klier and Ralek⁵ and Coughlan *et al.*¹⁰. These authors have offered different interpretations for their observations. Klier suggested that the slight shifts of wavelengths of NiA-zeolites indicate that the aquo-complex in the aluminosilicate is not quite the same as that in solution. Parsons and Drickamer²¹ reported that the band maxima of $\text{Ni}(\text{H}_2\text{O})_6^{2+}$ complex in salt solution shifts towards higher energy with increasing pressure on the complex. According to Klier²², it seems that hexahydrate Ni^{2+} ion in type A-zeolite is in a positive pressure field, expanding the complex and lowering effectively the crystal field splitting parameters. Thomas²³ observed slight shifts of bands of hydrated NiA-zeolites. But here as compared to Thomas' observation we recorded rather big hypsochromic shifts of band maxima, for example, in case of fully hydrated $\text{Ni}_{3.9}\text{A}$ up to $\sim 1450 \text{cm}^{-1}$. Thomas suggested that these shifts are perhaps due to osmotic pressure and hydrostatic tension existing within the zeolite cavities. In this case it is suggested that an increase in Ni^{2+} ions in the framework of zeolite type A, brings the hexaquo-complex of Ni^{2+} ions under pressure which causes band maxima to shift towards higher energy²¹, but the non-systematic behaviour of the shift has not been understood.

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